

METHODS USED IN FORMING NATIONAL ETIQUETTE SKILLS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS OF SPECIAL SCHOOLS

Oppoqxo'jayev Xojixuja Azimjon o'g'li

Teacher of the special pedagogical Department of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute named after Mukimi

Gmail: oppoqxojayevxojixuja@gmail.com

Yakubova Nozima Makhmudovna

Special pedagogy (speech therapy) 3 rd year student

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Abstract: this article talks about various methods and their application used in the formation of national etiquette skills in all types of special educational institutions.

Key words: method, national manners, encouragement, punishment, question-and-answer, interview, conversation, special educational institution.

The following methods are used in the formation of national union guests in primary class students of special schools:

1. Methods of explanation and storytelling. With the help of this method, by illuminating and revealing the importance of national etiquette skills in people's lives, their role in protecting their health and lives, in the elementary school students, they will information is generated. In the primary education system, based on the age and psychological characteristics of students, it is necessary to use this method to describe national etiquette skills and their content in a short, precise and clear manner.

2. Although it is similar to the explanatory method in terms of content, it has the ability to provide broader and more detailed information. Therefore, this method is effectively used to inform primary school students of special schools about the essence of national etiquette skills. The story, in most cases, is given by the teacher specialist or parents in the existing literature, as well as in the form of oral narration of the exemplary events that happened in life. In the explanation, attention is mainly paid to revealing the meaning of the concepts, and if scientific, scientific and popular terms are used, figurative expressions and quotations can be used in the narration.

3. Interview method. This method is used in primary education in order to create understanding of national etiquette skills by organizing live communication between students and teachers, parents or specialists. The advantage of the method is that it is possible to assess the extent to which information on national etiquette skills is being mastered by students during the conversation. If the students do not sufficiently master the given material or information, then there is an opportunity to re-explain.

4. Method of working with textbooks and resources. According to their age and psychological characteristics, elementary school students effectively absorb information and knowledge through visual receptors rather than through auditory receptors. Therefore, in the use of this method, these characteristics are taken into account, and during the test period, sources that reflect more national etiquette skills and their essence are referred to. When using this method, explanatory and storytelling methods are also used.

5. Method of demonstration. This method serves to ensure that primary school students of special schools directly perceive educational materials through clear images. The use of textbooks on the topic of national etiquette skills, special literature or resources, as well as

slide films and slides will help to achieve the expected results. In the information society, the use of computer technologies and the opportunities of the international information network of the Internet is considered particularly effective in forming a sense of respect for national etiquette skills in primary school students. After all, the possibilities of computer technology and the international information network of the Internet make it possible to choose and successfully deliver suitable materials for special school students based on their age and psychological capabilities.

6. Method of visual presentation. This method also serves to illuminate theoretical information about national etiquette skills and their essence in a figurative way with the help of visual and visual tools. The method of visual representation can be used in different ways. Including: 1. Relying on subjective activities (behavior, example of parents, teachers, peers, surrounding persons) in elucidating the essence of national-ethic skills; 2. Distribution of visual materials explaining the content of national etiquette skills to a group of students; 3. General display of images (pictures, tables) that tell about national etiquette skills with the help of computer technology.

7. Excursion method. This method is used to strengthen and enrich the theoretical information acquired by primary school students of special schools. Excursions were arranged in order to ensure that elementary school students of special schools move together in cinemas, public places, (public catering establishments, public transport), streets and roads in schools with experimental sites for conducting the research. . Class leaders, Methodist teachers involved in the trial work, science teachers, and dissertation students were in charge of organizing the excursions. Also, responsible persons are determined from the employees of cinemas, public catering establishments, car companies, and the State Vehicle Control Service (VCS). With their help, students were able to enrich and strengthen their theoretical knowledge of national etiquette skills.

8. Example method. This method is used to raise respect for social and legal norms in primary school students of special schools using the most effective method of educational influence - example. During the research period, the following social subjects were taught to elementary school students of special schools about behavior in public places, compliance with traffic rules, taking into account technical and life safety requirements, organizing class duty: science teachers, class it was taken into account that the leader, parents, responsible persons and their peers can also set an example. In addition, folklore was used as a teaching tool for elementary school students with examples of folk oral creativity and real life examples. During the test work, attention was paid to the observance of national etiquette skills by the primary school students of special schools based on weaving stories and fairy tales with the participation of their favorite artistic characters.

9. Training method. This method, as in the case of individuals of all ages, the application of the acquired theoretical knowledge of the norms of national etiquette in the elementary school students of special schools helps to master the skills of adhering to them in everyday life. In the course of the experiment, students performed collective, group, and individual exercises on observing national etiquette standards. Among such exercises, it is possible to show exercises such as "How to behave in public places", "Etiquette of hospitality", "Attitude towards adults and children", "Show love to parents".

10. Method of practical training. This method also helps to strengthen and enrich the knowledge of the primary school students of the special institution about the norms of national etiquette, and help them to form the skills to follow them in everyday life. During the testing, special attention was paid to the organization of practical exercises in the form of games and competitions to train the students of the primary school of the special institution to observe the national etiquette standards. Among such games, one can mention table games created by the author called "Let's bring road signs to life", "Create new road signs", as well as "Proper movement on city streets". Competitions such as "The most well-educated young passenger", "The most exemplary spectator", and "The most exemplary singer" not only ensured the thorough assimilation of national etiquette standards by the primary school students of the special institution, but also created interest in them about the processes of being in public places and traveling on public transport.

11. Game method. According to their age and psychological characteristics, primary school students of special institutions effectively absorb the social experience gained by mankind with the help of their activities. That is, they learn the skills of following the existing national etiquette standards based on practical activities enriched with game elements. In the organization of the test work, the games proposed by various authors who infused the essence of national etiquette standards into their content, as well as based on the personal creative approach of the dissertation, were used effectively and purposefully. These include interactive intellectual games such as "Discussion on various topics", "Let's get acquainted!", and "Let's eat together".

12. Method of promotion. This method is used in order to effectively form the skills of strict adherence to national etiquette standards and obedience to existing procedures in elementary school students of a special institution. Observance of national etiquette standards, showing respect for them was encouraged or punished through direct and indirect observation and assessment of students' actions and daily activities. In the period of the test work, students' behavior is encouraged by encouraging and encouraging, giving confidence, expressing gratitude, and rewarding.

13. Punishment methods. It is known from educational practice that students do not always follow existing social requirements and rules. At the same time, they are not always able to rationally evaluate or ignore the consequences of not observing the norms of national etiquette. In the daily activities of the elementary school students of the special institution, non-observance of national decency norms and disrespect for them were used as methods of punishment such as reprimanding, scolding, and shaming. Attention was paid to the individual application of punishment methods to students. Consequently, when this approach is taken, students who do not follow the existing procedures will not lose their reputation in front of their peers and classmates, and therefore their negative behavior will not go unpunished.

14. Question and answer method. This method was used to analyze and assess the level of effective assimilation of the presented material by students in the process of mastering knowledge of national etiquette standards. When applying the method, special attention was paid to the short, precise, and clear questions directed to the students' attention. Two-level questions were used in conducting the research. That is, 1) questions about recognition; 2) extraction questions.

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